

Correction

Correction: Molina et al. Storm Energy Flux Characterization along the Mediterranean Coast of Andalusia (Spain). *Water* 2019, 11, 509

Rosa Molina ¹

¹ Department of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Marine and Environmental Sciences, University of Cádiz, Polígono del Río San Pedro s/n, 11510 Puerto Real, Spain; r.molina.gil@gmail.com (R.M.); giorgio.anfuso@uca.es (G.A.)

² Department of Engineering, University of Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, Bd. 8, 90128 Palermo, Italy; giorgio.manno@unipa.it (G.M.); giuseppe.ciraolo@unipa.it (G.C.)

* Correspondence: carlo.lore@unipa.it; Tel.: +39-238-965-24

In the original article [1], there was a mistake in Table 1 (page seven) as published. The total energy (E_{tot}) unit of measurement of the third column of the table was [Wh/m]. The table was corrected by replacing [Wh/m] with [kWh/m].

The corrected Table 1 appears below. The authors apologize for any inconvenience caused and state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. The original article has been updated.

Table 1. Storm characteristics at each prediction point: class, energy (E_{tot}), frequency of storms, significant wave height (H_{m0}), peak period (T_p), and duration (D).

Point	Class	E_{tot} [kWh/m]			Frequency [%]	H_{m0} [m]		T_p [s]	D [days]
		Min	Max	Mean	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Mean	
1	I	108	503	265	59.6	2.01	0.26	6.5	0.9
	II	503	1100	730	27.8	2.61	0.37	7.4	1.9
	III	1100	2102	1509	8.3	3.27	0.48	8.1	2.9
	IV	2102	4179	2624	3.5	3.64	0.65	8.5	4.2
	V	4179	9165	5635	0.7	4.68	0.98	9.7	4.8
2	I	108	503	272	58.9	2.05	0.29	6.5	0.9
	II	503	1100	749	27.6	2.65	0.38	7.4	2.0
	III	1100	2102	1484	9.9	3.13	0.50	7.9	3.3
	IV	2102	4179	2752	2.3	3.76	0.62	8.6	4.8
	V	4179	9165	5551	0.4	4.73	0.76	9.2	6.9
3	I	108	503	270	55.0	2.05	0.28	6.5	0.9
	II	503	1100	739	28.0	2.69	0.39	7.4	1.9
	III	1100	2102	1460	12.4	3.22	0.47	8.0	3.1
	IV	2102	4179	2775	3.4	3.99	0.52	8.9	4.4
	V	4179	9165	5632	0.9	4.87	0.74	9.5	7.0
4	I	108	503	280	67.1	2.03	0.27	6.8	0.9
	II	503	1100	712	23.2	2.52	0.35	7.6	2.0
	III	1100	2102	1408	8.3	3.12	0.46	8.3	3.0
	IV	2102	4179	2802	0.9	4.34	0.60	9.6	3.3
	V	4179	9165	5248	0.3	5.18	0.49	10.6	3.7

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Reference

1. Molina, R.; Manno, G.; Lo Re, C.; Anfuso, G.; Ciruolo, G. Storm Energy Flux Characterization along the Mediterranean Coast of Andalusia (Spain). *Water* 2019, 11, 509. [[CrossRef](#)]